

Role of Teacher-Students Relationship in Students Academic Achievement at Secondary Level

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Abstract

This study was conducted on the role of teacher-students relationship in student's academic achievement at secondary level. The objectives of study were to investigate the role of teacher-students relationship in promoting student's critical thinking at secondary level. To find out academic achievement of students at secondary level. The study was quantitative in nature and descriptive method used to conduct the study. Survey technique was used to collect the data from the respondents. The population of the study consisted of twelve hundred and twenty seven (1227) male and female students in the Kotli city. The researcher used simple random sampling technique for the selection of the sample (300). The researcher selected three hundred (300) male and female as a sample of the study. A five-point Likert-scale questionnaire was used as a tool in this study. The reliability of the instrument was 0.80. The researcher personally visited the schools of city Kotli Azad Jammu and Kashmir and collected the data. Statistical Package for Social Sciences software (SPSS) was used for the analysis of data. The researcher applied frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation for the analysis of data.

Keywords: Teacher-student's relationship, Academic achievement, Secondary level

Introduction

The relationship between teachers and students greatly affects how students feel, act, and perform in school. Teachers interact with students daily, and these interactions can either support or harm their development. These moments determine whether the relationship is good or bad. That's why teachers should be careful about how they talk and connect with each student to create a positive and helpful learning environment. That's why teachers need to be mindful of how they communicate and engage with each student to build a supportive learning environment (Göktaş & Kaya, 2023).

However, certain challenges can make difficult for teachers to develop positive relationships with students. These barriers can create misunderstandings or conflicts, which may negatively affect students' learning and performance. Research by Magro, *et al.*, (2024) found that when students experience conflict with their teachers, their academic progress often suffers (Falk, Shephard, & Mendenhall, 2022).

To overcome these challenges, teachers use different strategies to improve their relationships with students. By understanding the difficulties that may arise and learning effective ways to handle them, teachers can create a more positive classroom atmosphere. This can lead to better interactions, stronger connections, and improved student success (Kilbane & Milman, 2024).

The motivational model by Gyeltshen, (2021) explains how teachers can build good relationships with students. It gives ideas on how teachers can connect with students and understand them better. This helps teachers stay calm when students act out or show disrespect. Conteraras, *et al.*, (2014) also suggest that teachers should make the classroom a friendly place where students feel accepted and are more likely to join in discussions. A happy and positive environment is very important for creating strong teacher-student relationships (Frank, 2022).

Many factors outside the classroom also influence these relationships. Research studied how teachers' characteristics affect student motivation, as well as the role of student independence, parental involvement, and a sense of belonging in academic success. Similarly, found that strong teacher-student relationships contribute to a positive school experience (Boonmoh, Jumpakate, & Karpklon, 2021).

Since students spend a lot of time with their teachers, their experiences in school are shaped by these relationships. The section "Role of Teachers' Support on Students' Motivation and Engagement" explains that students engage in learning differently based on their interactions with teachers. These interactions also influence how much students learn and benefit from their education (Roorda, *et al.*, 2011).

A country's success is closely connected to its education system, which helps shape the values and behavior of its people. Saxer, *et al.*, (2024) believe that investing in education is necessary for a better future worldwide. Education is considered the most powerful tool for achieving national goals, helping individuals become part of society, and promoting progress in different areas like political stability, economic growth, scientific development, cultural awareness, and technology (Aysan, Canga, & Kayani, 2024).

The success of any education system, whether in a developed or developing country, depends on the planners, managers, and teachers who run it. According to Gyeltshen, (2021), teachers play a key role in shaping a nation's future by developing skilled and responsible individuals. Alam and Mohanty (2023) state that "no education system can be better than the quality of its teachers."

Students' academic success is greatly influenced by their schools and teachers. If a student performs poorly, it could be due to the student, teacher, or school environment. A study by Robinson, (2022) found that a positive relationship between teachers and students can improve academic performance. Students who show more interest and have a positive attitude tend to perform better in school. On the other hand, Wikipedia (2021) describes academic performance as how well students, teachers, or schools meet their educational goals (Hidayatullah & Csíkos, 2024).

Kim (2021) explains that a strong teacher-student relationship is built on several key qualities. These include clear communication, a safe and supportive classroom, mutual respect, patience, fairness, and giving students timely encouragement. Teachers who demonstrate these qualities are more likely to be well-liked by their students (Nonyelum, Ogugua, & Abah, 2022).

Role of teacher-student relationships at the secondary level in Kotli has been identified as a critical thing influencing students academic achievement and overall school experience. However many secondary school students experience negative relationships with their teachers, characterized by low levels of emotional support, high levels of conflict, and limited opportunities for student autonomy and engagement. Despite the importance of teacher-student relationships, there is a lack of understanding about the specific thing that contribute to positive and negative relationships in secondary level students of Kotli. Furthermore, there is a need to explore the perspectives and experiences of both teachers and students to gain a deeper understanding of the complex dynamics involved in teacher-student relationships at secondary level.

Delimitation of the Study

This study was delimited to:

- i. Students of Secondary level at Kotli AJ&K.
- ii. Academic Achievement of Secondary school 2022 and 2023.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study focuses on how the quality of teacher-student relationships influences students' academic achievement at the secondary level. A positive, supportive relationship can boost student motivation, confidence, and classroom engagement. It highlights key factors such as communication, trust, and emotional support. These elements together play a crucial role in shaping students' academic performance and success.

Research Methodology

The study was quantitative in nature and descriptive method was used for this study. In this study cross sectional survey technique was used to collect the data from the respondents. All the male and female students of secondary level in city Kotli AJ&K were the population of the study. There are total number of 16 schools in Kotli, including 7 boys and 9 girls. Sample random sampling technique was used for selection of sample. Sample was selected according to Kerjcie and Morgan (1970) table. Three hundred students were selected as sample of the study. As the major aim of the study was to measure the teacher-students' relationship on students' academic achievement so the researcher used standardized questionnaire based on the dimensions of teacher-students' relationship. Five-point Likert scale was to collect the responses from the respondents. Questionnaire were consisted on 25 items. The questionnaire was validated by two experts from the Department of Education, University of Kotli Azad Jammu and Kashmir. For the purpose

of pilot testing, the questionnaire was distributed among 30 secondary school students who are not the part of final survey. The purpose of pilot testing was to check the readability and reliability of instrument. Reliability of instrument was checked by Cronbach's alpha value which is 0.80 using statistical package for social sciences SPSS software (version 22). The researcher collected the data personally visited the secondary level schools of both Male and Female students in city Kotli Azad Jammu and Kashmir. Statistical package for social sciences software (SPSS) used for the analysis of data. Data was analyzed by using percentage, mean score, frequency, and standard deviation.

Data Analysis

Table 1: I Admire My Teachers

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	147	95	16	36	6	4.14	1.090
Students	300	%	49.0	31.7	5.3	12.0		

Table 1 indicates that 80.7% (49.0%SA+31.7%A) of respondents were agreed with the statement that "I admire my teachers". Furthermore, the mean score (M=4.14) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 2: My Teacher Has a Positive Attitude On a Daily Basis

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	91	155	11	32	11	3.94	1.047
Students	300	%	30.3	51.7	3.7	10.7		

Table 2 indicates that 82% (30.3%SA+51.7%A) of respondents were agreed with the statement that "My teacher has a positive attitude on a daily basis". Furthermore, the mean score (M=3.94) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 3 My teacher presents the information in a way that is easy to understand.

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	121	125	19	27	8	4.08	1.031
Students	300	%	40.3	41.7	6.3	9.0		

Table 3 indicates that 82% (40.3%SA+41.7%A) of respondents were agreed with the statement that "My teacher presents the information in a way that is easy to understand". Furthermore, the mean score (M=4.08) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 4: My Teacher Cares About My Academic And Social Well-Being

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	97	131	21	47	4	3.90	1.065
Students	300	%	32.3	43.7	7.0	15.7		

Table 4 indicates that 76% (32.3%SA+43.7%A) of respondents were agreed with the statement that "My teacher cares about my academic and social well-being". Furthermore, the mean score (M=3.90) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 5: My Teacher Is Sensitive To All Students

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	140	125	15	16	4	4.27	.883
Sample	300 %	46.7	41.7	5.0	5.3	1.3		

Table 5 indicates that 88.4% (46.7%SA+41.7%A) of respondents agreed with the statement that "My teacher is sensitive to all students". Furthermore, the mean score (M=4.27) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 6: My Teacher Views Me As An Important Part Of The Classroom

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	84	119	31	57	9	3.71	1.154
Students	300 %	28.0	39.7	10.3	19.0	3.0		

Table 6 indicates that 67.7% (28.0%SA+39.7%A) of respondents agreed with the statement that "My teacher views me as an important part of the classroom". Furthermore, the mean score (M=3.71) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 7: My Teacher Motivates Me To Give My Best Effort

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	113	127	11	35	14	3.97	1.142
Students	79 %	37.7	42.3	3.7	11.7	4.7		

Table 7 indicates that 80% (37.7%SA+42.3%A) of respondents agreed with the statement that "My teacher motivates me to give my best effort". Furthermore, the mean score (M=3.97) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 8: My Teacher Provides Support For All Students

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	103	119	12	52	14	3.82	1.212
Sample	300 %	34.3	39.7	4.0	17.3	4.7		

Table 8 indicates that 74% (34.3%SA+39.7%A) of respondents agreed with the statement that "My teacher provides support for all students". Furthermore, the mean score (M=3.82) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 9: My Teacher Uses Various Cultural Activities In The Lessons, Like Experimentation, Case Studies, Live

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	1	13	38	111	137	1.77	.857
Sample	79 %	0.3	4.3	12.7	37.0	45.7		

Table 9 indicates that 4.6% (0.3%SA+4.3%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that "My teacher uses various cultural activities in the lessons, like experimentation, case studies, live". Furthermore, the mean score (M=1.77) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 10: My Teacher Guides Students In a Positive Direction For Their Personal Growth.

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	105	157	13	22	3	4.13	.873
Sample	300 %	35.0	52.3	4.3	7.3	1.0		

Table 10 indicates that 87.3% (35.0%SA+52.3%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that “My teacher guides students in a positive direction for their personal growth”. Furthermore, the mean score (M 4.13) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 11: My Teacher Encourages Student Feedback

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	118	127	21	27	7	4.07	1.016
Sample	300 %	39.3	42.3	7.0	9.0	2.3		

Table 11 indicates that 81.6% (39.3%SA+42.3%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that “My teacher encourages student feedback”. Furthermore, the mean score (M 4.07) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 12: My Teacher Acknowledges Student Effort Through Recognition And Praise

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	116	123	7	34	20	3.94	1.210
Students	300 %	38.7	41.0	2.3	11.3	6.7		

Table 12 indicates that 79.7% (38.7%SA+41.0%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that “My teacher acknowledges student effort through recognition and praise”. Furthermore, the mean score (M=3.94) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 13 My teacher uses examples of student background experiences, beliefs, and knowledge.

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	109	148	10	21	12	4.07	1.017
Students	300 %	36.3	49.3	3.3	7.0	4.0		

Table 13 indicates that 85.6 (36.3%SA+49.3%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that “My teacher uses examples of student background experiences, beliefs, and knowledge”. Furthermore, the mean score (M 4.07) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 14; My Teacher Provides High And Clear Expectations For Academic Performance

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	78	175	15	25	7	3.97	.925

Students 300 % 26.0 58.3 5.0 8.3 2.3

Table 14 indicates that 84.3% (26.0%SA+58.3%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that “My teacher provides high and clear expectations for academic performance”. Furthermore, the mean score (M 3.97) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 15: My Teacher Takes The Time To Assist Individual Students That Need Help

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	108	127	8	25	32	3.85	1.289
Students	300	%	36.0	42.3	2.7	8.3		

Table 15 indicates that 78.3% (36.0%SA+42.3%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that “My teacher takes the time to assist individual students that need help”. Furthermore, the mean score (M 3.85) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 16: My Teacher Motivates Students Through Inspiring Teaching

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	5	22	24	74	175	1.69	1.008
Students	300	%	1.7	7.3	8.0	24.7		

Table 16 indicates that 9% (1.7%SA+7.3%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that “My teacher motivates students through inspiring teaching”. Furthermore, the mean score (M 1.69) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 17: My Teacher Makes Teaching Attractive By Showing How Theory Is Implemented In The Real World

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	77	73	42	52	56	3.21	1.467
Students	300	%	25.7	24.3	14.0	17.3		

Table 17 indicates that 50% (25.7%SA+24.3%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that “My teacher makes teaching attractive by showing how theory is implemented in the real world”. Furthermore, the mean score (M=3.21) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 18: I Am Able To Take Risks In The Classroom Without Feeling Embarrassed

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	4	13	23	59	201	1.53	.908
Sample	300	%	1.3	4.3	7.7	19.7		

Table 18 indicates that 5.6% (1.3%SA+4.3%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that “I am able to take risks in the classroom without feeling embarrassed”. Furthermore, the mean score (M=1.53) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 19: I Enjoy Coming To My Teacher's Classroom

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	121	138	9	18	14	4.11	1.041
Students	300 %	40.3	46.3	3.0	6.0	4.7		

Table 19 indicates that 86.6% (40.3%SA+46.3%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that "I enjoy coming to my teacher's classroom". Furthermore, the mean score (M=4.11) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 20: I Feel That My Teacher Is a Coach, Mentor, Or Partner

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	98	139	12	35	16	3.89	1.143
Students	300 %	32.7	46.3	4.0	11.7	5.3		

Table 20 indicates that 78.7% (32.7%SA+46.0%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that "I feel that my teacher is a coach, mentor, or partner". Furthermore, the mean score (M 3.89) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 21: I am Able To Ask For Assistance Without Fear Of Rejection Or Embarrassment.

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	9	13	37	70	171	1.73	1.033
Students	300 %	3.0	4.3	12.3	23.3	57.0		

Table 21 indicates that 7.3% (3.0%SA+4.3%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that "I am able to ask for assistance without fear of rejection or embarrassment". Furthermore, the mean score (M=1.73) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 22: My Teacher Connects Emotionally With The Students

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	113	152	13	13	9	4.16	.917
Students	300 %	37.7	50.7	4.3	4.3	3.0		

Table 22 indicates that 88.4% (37.7%SA+50.7%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that "My teacher connects emotionally with the students". Furthermore, the mean score (M 4.16) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 23: My Teacher Expects Me To Succeed

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
N	F	141	126	14	15	4	4.28	.871
Students	300 %	47.0	42.0	4.7	5.0	1.3		

Table 23 indicates that 89% (47.0%SA+42.0%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that "My teacher expects me to succeed". Furthermore, the mean score (M 4.28) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 24: My Teacher Makes Positive Comments About The Students' Abilities To Learn.

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
	N	69	83	56	86	6	3.41	1.183
Students	300 %	23.0	27.7	18.7	28.7	2.0		

Table 24 indicates that 50.7% (23.0%SA+27.7%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that "My teacher makes positive comments about the students' abilities to learn". Furthermore, the mean score (M=3.41) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement

Table 25: My Teacher Has a Good Attitude

Sample Group		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
	N	146	79	15	37	23	3.96	1.313
Students	300 %	48.7	26.3	5.0	12.3	7.7		

Table 25 indicates that 75% (48.7%SA+26.3%A) of respondent were agreed with the statement that "My teacher has a good attitude". Furthermore, the mean score (M=3.96) of respondents also reflects the opinion in favor of the statement.

Table 26: Academic Achievement

Sr. No	Academic Years	Mean	SD
1.	(2022)	104.8350	16.67113
2.	(2023)		

Table 26 indicates that academic achievement of students (Mean=104.8350, SD=16.67113).

Discussion

The findings of this study highlight the powerful role that teachers play in shaping the academic success and emotional well-being of their students. When teachers maintain a positive attitude, communicate clearly, and show genuine care for their students, they create a supportive and engaging learning environment. This kind of atmosphere helps students feel more connected to their teachers, enjoy learning, and feel motivated to do their best. As a result, students are more likely to succeed both in school and in their personal development. Another important finding is the value of empathy and inclusiveness in the classroom. Teachers who treat all students as important members of the class, provide regular support, and encourage them to try their best help create a sense of belonging. These supportive teachers make students feel valued and capable, which boosts their confidence and helps them reach their full potential. A caring and inclusive environment can make a big difference in how students feel about school and their ability to succeed.

The study also shows that using real-life examples, cultural activities, and active teaching methods makes learning more meaningful and interesting for students. When teachers acknowledge students' efforts, encourage feedback, and help them grow personally, it leads to a respectful and motivating classroom culture. These practices not only improve academic learning but also help students feel proud of their achievements and responsible for their learning. Moreover, when teachers recognize students' unique backgrounds and set clear goals, while also giving individual support, they ensure every

student has a chance to do well. It is also important that students feel safe to express themselves, ask questions, and take risks in their learning without fear. A classroom where students feel emotionally secure is more likely to support growth, participation, and deeper learning. Finally, strong teacher-student relationships built on encouragement, emotional connection, and positive feedback lead to better outcomes. When students feel supported, respected, and believed in, they are more likely to be motivated and confident. Teachers who inspire, guide, and show a positive attitude help build a classroom where students not only learn but thrive both academically and personally.

Conclusion

The results of this study clearly show that students hold positive perceptions of their teachers in many key areas related to classroom behavior, teaching methods, and emotional support. A large majority of respondents expressed admiration for their teachers and acknowledged their positive attitudes and efforts. For example, more than 80% of students agreed that their teachers are admirable, positive, and present lessons clearly, which shows strong appreciation for the personal and professional qualities of their instructors. Students also reported feeling supported both academically and emotionally. A high percentage agreed that their teachers care about their well-being, motivate them, and guide them toward personal growth. Notably, over 88% agreed that their teachers connect emotionally with students, and a similar percentage felt that their teachers expect them to succeed. These findings suggest that students recognize their teachers not only as educators but also as mentors and role models.

However, a few areas of concern were identified. Responses showed low agreement regarding classroom risk-taking, use of cultural activities, and students' comfort in asking for assistance without embarrassment. These lower scores indicate that some students may not feel fully safe or included when it comes to participation, sharing ideas, or exploring learning in diverse ways. These are important areas where improvements can be made to promote a more inclusive and supportive classroom environment. In summary, while the study highlights the strengths of the teaching environment especially in motivation, emotional support, and clarity of instruction it also points to the need for increased efforts in fostering classroom inclusivity, cultural responsiveness, and psychological safety. Addressing these gaps can help ensure that all students feel respected, valued, and empowered in their learning journey.

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